

Natural Flood Management Monitoring Tool

Developed by:

YORKSHIRE DALES
National Park Authority

Natural Flood Management Monitoring Tool

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Introduction

Natural flood management (NFM) involves working with the natural features of a catchment, aiming to replicate its natural processes to reduce flood risk. It has the potential to reduce and delay the downstream flood peak during rainfall events, meaning more time to prepare and mitigate flood events. It is most effective for high frequency, low magnitude flooding events, for example 1-in-2 year flooding (Wingfield *et al.*, 2019). NFM may work most effectively where several interventions are used collectively throughout the catchment (YDNPA, 2017). As well as flood-related benefits, NFM can have wider benefits including carbon sequestration and habitat creation. As the level of discrete funding opportunities have increased, NFM is increasingly being used in catchments in the UK.

Payment for Outcomes (PfO) is the principle of paying farmers for achieving specific outcomes, as opposed to simply paying them for implementing NFM interventions. It is, therefore, important to understand how the effectiveness and outcomes of different NFM interventions can be monitored, as this provides a basis for determining payment rates (Richardson *et al.*, 2020a). This approach is becoming more widely adopted, with increasing recognition of the importance of working with and protecting nature, as opposed to exploiting it in a way where our demand exceeds what it can supply (Dasgupta, 2021). To this end, PfO approaches act as a financial incentive for farmers and landowners to manage land in a more sustainable, environmentally-friendly way. Monitoring the outcomes of NFM is also crucial to informing policy, particularly as the UK is beginning to develop its own policies, such as the Environmental Land Management Scheme, following the UK's departure from the EU.

Monitoring is key to this approach; it is crucial that the impacts of NFM interventions are ascertained to measure their success, so that payments can be released, and bands or rates of payments are suitably informed by evidence. Monitoring these interventions is also important because NFM is still a relatively new concept, so it can help inform and validate efforts to determine the impacts of different interventions. For these reasons, this monitoring tool has been created to present information about monitoring NFM in a clear, accessible way.

The following tool showcases ways to monitor interventions detailed in the Yorkshire Dales National Park Authority (YDNPA) NFM Farmers' Guide (2017). As it is designed to aid farmers and landowners in deciding which NFM interventions they may wish to implement, there is a focus on farm-level NFM interventions. It provides information about the feasibility and logistics of monitoring each intervention as part of a PfO scheme. At this stage, payment rates are not determined. Landscape level interventions are not considered within this tool, but the user is directed to further information on other NFM interventions where these are beyond its own scope. This is an evolving research base, and as such this is a working document which will be updated as is appropriate.

Instructions for use

This tool is designed to provide information about monitoring NFM interventions. Simply click on your desired outcome below and work through the linked flow chart. You can then click on the suggested NFM option(s) to learn more about monitoring them.

What is your main desired outcome of Natural Flood Management (NFM)?

Slow the flow of water towards and within the watercourse.

Increase water storage on floodplains

Improve soil infiltration / water storage

Reduce overland flow

Interception of water before it reaches the watercourse

Reduce flood peak and volume.

Improve soil condition.

Additional benefits

N.B. When used in this tool, the term 'watercourse' denotes rivers as well as smaller streams and gullies.

Desired Outcome: Slow the flow of water towards and within the watercourse.

Desired Outcome: Increase water storage on floodplains.

Desired Outcome: Improve soil infiltration / water storage.

Desired Outcome: Reduce overland flow.

Desired Outcome: Interception of water before it reaches the watercourse.

Desired Outcome: Reduce flood peak and volume.

Desired Outcome: Improve soil condition

Desired Outcome: Additional Benefits

NFM interventions can have several additional benefits, as are briefly outlined in the table below. Please note that this is not a complete coverage of such benefits and, in some cases, there may be confounding factors. Information in this table was taken from the Environment Agency (Burgess-Gamble *et al.*, 2018); for more detailed benefits of the interventions please see the [Evidence Directory document](#).

	Social Benefits (Health benefits, aesthetic values, cultural qualities etc.)	Improved water quality	Greenhouse gas reduction	Habitat provision
<i>Blocking drainage grips</i>	The return to a more 'natural' state can improve the recreational and aesthetic values of the area.	This can increase trapping of sediment and reduce the pollution being mobilised to watercourses.	This may reduce the amount of carbon being lost to watercourses, making the area a more effective carbon sink.	This can create habitats for vegetation such as Sphagnum mosses, as well as a range of other species.
<i>Bunds, swales, and scrapes</i>	The improvements to habitat may attract visitors.	These capture sediment and pollutants, reducing the amount reaching watercourses.	There is little evidence for this benefit.	These features and associated detention areas may provide habitats.
<i>Creating and managing buffer strips</i>	Can improve accessibility for visitors. Their 'natural' look also gives them aesthetic value.	Buffer strips can reduce phosphorous, nitrogen, organic matter, and suspended sediment.	Vegetation may reduce atmospheric greenhouse gases and produce oxygen.	These may be important for invertebrate habitats, plant diversity, and habitat connectivity.
<i>Cross drains in farm tracks</i>	There is little evidence for this benefit.	These help to protect against erosion and sediment loss to watercourses.	There is little evidence for this benefit.	There is little evidence for this benefit.
<i>Increasing soil permeability/water holding capacity</i>	There is little evidence for this benefit.	Increased infiltration means fewer pollutants reach watercourses in runoff.	Increased soil health may improve its ability to reduce greenhouse gases.	Healthier soil may provide a habitat for some new species.
<i>Leaky woody dams</i>	Habitat provision can be an opportunity for education and tourism. More available fish for angling may increase recreational activity and its economic benefits.	These can help filter sediment and pollutants out of the river. They have been seen to reduce phosphorous and nitrogen levels.	These dams may sequester carbon in the long term.	They cause a greater range of flow velocities and create pools. These habitats can support a variety of species.

<i>Livestock management/reducing stock</i>	This may improve the aesthetic value of the area.	This can reduce the amount of sedimentation and diffuse water pollution from agriculture.	The resultant improvements to soil can increase its carbon storage ability. There is also a reduction in the amount of greenhouse gases released from intensive agriculture.	Diversifying land use by reducing the intensity of livestock grazing is likely to increase habitats.
<i>Mob grazing</i>	There is little evidence for this benefit.	Less fertiliser / pesticide is used, reducing the pollution reaching watercourses.	The soil health is improved, increasing its ability to sequester carbon.	The improved soil increases vegetation growth and habitat provision.
<i>Planting and managing hedgerows</i>	These are seen as 'natural,' so increase the area's aesthetic value.	Hedges can reduce soil loss and pollution due to erosion.	These can increase the ability of soil to uptake and sequester carbon and other greenhouse gases.	These may provide cover and food sources for different species.
<i>Planting and managing trees</i>	Trees have been shown to improve both physical and mental health. They provide a range of aesthetic, cultural and recreational values.	Woodlands generally have low inputs of fertiliser / pesticide, so water quality is protected. They may also trap and retain pollutants from runoff.	Trees are a significant carbon store and regulate atmospheric CO ₂ considerably.	Planting trees is a very effective way to create habitats for a variety of species. Many priority species are associated with living in such areas.
<i>Restoring meanders</i>	Restoring natural river features attracts visitors who can reap benefits from the area and use it for recreation.	Meanders have been shown to reduce levels of nitrogen and phosphorous.	When combined with revegetation, this may provide a sink for carbon and other pollutants.	The increased range of flow velocities improves the diversity of habitats and makes the river more ecological resistant.
<i>Sediment traps</i>	There is little evidence for this benefit.	These can filter out sediment and nutrients, reducing pollution of the watercourse.	There is little evidence for this benefit.	There is little evidence for this benefit.
<i>Storage ponds</i>	These may attract visitors. There is a high per hectare recreational value for such areas.	These ponds can help capture sediment nutrients in the water.	Carbon can be captured and sequestered in the ponds; they are a carbon sink.	These ponds can provide a habitat for a variety of species.
<i>Winter cover crops</i>	There is little evidence for this benefit.	Planting a winter cover crop has been shown to reduce leaching (e.g. of nitrogen)	These can increase the ability of soil to uptake and sequester carbon and other greenhouse gases.	These can help create seasonal diversity and provide shelter and food for bird species.

Possible NFM Interventions

The following pages contain information about the interventions below:

Blocking drainage grips

(Credit: M Reed)

Bunds, swales, and scrapes

(Credit: Don Catchment Rivers Trust)

Creating and managing buffer strips

(Credit: T Wilson)

Cross drains in farm tracks

(Credit: H Keep)

Increasing soil permeability/water holding capacity

(Credit: L Firbank)

Leaky woody dams

(Credit: J Armstrong)

Livestock management/reducing stock

(Credit: P Leeder)

Mob grazing

(Credit: Soil Association Scotland)

Planting and managing hedgerows

(Credit: Don Catchment Rivers Trust)

Planting and managing trees

(Credit: S Ballard)

Restoring meanders

(Credit: H Keep)

Sediment traps

(Credit: YDRT)

Storage ponds

(Credit: Don Catchment Rivers Trust)

Winter cover crops

(Credit: L Firbank)

For each intervention, there is a short description, a list of flood-related outcomes, and details about the possibility of monitoring as part of a Payment for Outcomes (PfO) scheme. Links to further information are also provided.

This is not an exhaustive list of possible NFM interventions, other options are explained in the following documents:

- [Working with Natural Processes – Evidence Directory](#)
- [Natural Flood Management Handbook](#)
- [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers](#)

The above documents informed the descriptions of the NFM interventions outlined in the following pages. Information about outcomes of interventions and monitoring possibilities was taken from Richardson *et al.* (2020b). It is important to consider the value of having a variety of NFM interventions throughout the catchment. Whilst small-scale interventions on a land parcel may not always be seen to have a great impact on their own, they are crucial to taking a more holistic approach to NFM, whereby interventions can have a collective impact across the catchment (Burgess-Gamble *et al.*, 2018).

N.B. There is a possibility for using Geographical Information Systems (GIS) for the monitoring of some NFM interventions, which would require someone with a skillset in GIS. However, where this applies, it is only an alternative to the other monitoring methods suggested.

Blocking drainage grips*

This involves creating water storage in the grips. There can be a secondary benefit through encouraging development of peatland which increases soil water storage and acts as a carbon sink.

Outcomes

- Slow the flow of water towards and within the watercourse.
- Increase water storage in uplands
- Interception of water before it reaches the river
- Improve soil condition.
- **Additional benefits:** social benefits, improved water quality, greenhouse gas reduction, and habitat provision

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a Pfo Scheme
<i>Slowing flow</i>	Flow rate and storage duration measured using time lapse photography (camera, gauge board and computer software to analyse footage). This needs to be checked after flood events.	Anyone trained who can allocate time. Validation by a specialist is required.	Some evidence of interventions working, but there is some uncertainty around sub-catchment or catchment scales. Moorlands may also cross ownership boundaries which could complicate payment.
<i>Storing water</i>	Volume and duration of water stored can be measured by taking photos (camera and stage board needed). Photos and data should be checked after flood events.	A specialist would be required to evaluate, but farmers can monitor ongoing performance.	

*This intervention is only applicable on moorlands.

Find out more about this intervention:

- Chapter 2.3.2 - [Natural Flood Management Handbook](#)
- Page 19 - [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers.](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Bunds, swales, and scrapes

These are features which store water and slowly release it once the storm has subsided.

Outcomes

- Slow the flow of water in the watercourse
- Increase water storage on floodplains
- **Additional benefits:** improved water quality and habitat provision

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a PfO Scheme
<i>Slowing flow</i>	Flow rate and storage duration measured using time lapse photography (camera, gauge board and computer). This needs to be checked after flood events.	Anyone trained who can allocate time. Validation by a specialist is required.	Some evidence of interventions working, but some variables are hard to measure (e.g. flow). More research would be needed to understand how payments could work. It is particularly difficult to distinguish the efforts of different farmers in contributing to downstream changes.
<i>Storing water</i>	Volume and duration of water stored can be measured by taking photos (camera and stage board needed). Photos and data should be checked after flood events.	A specialist would be required to evaluate, but farmers can monitor ongoing performance.	
<i>Filtering water</i>	Reductions in fine grained sediment can be measured with sampling and some laboratory analysis. This would need to be monitored monthly for adequate understanding of changes over time.	A specialist would be required given the laboratory element of this monitoring.	

Find out more about this intervention:

- Page 14 and 15 - [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers.](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Creating and managing buffer strips

Buffer strips are areas of grass or vegetation. Due to the increased surface roughness, they slow the flow and promote the deposition of sediment and associated nutrients. Often these are placed alongside watercourse to reduce the amount of water and sediment that reaches the watercourse. They can also be placed along field boundaries and are very effective when placed upstream.

Outcomes

- Reduce overland flow
- Interception of water before it reaches the river
- Increase stability of the soil and resistance to erosion
- **Additional benefits:** improved water quality, greenhouse gas reduction, and habitat provision

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a PfO Scheme
<i>Increasing roughness</i>	Vegetation height and width (i.e., density) can be measured using a tape measure or ruler. This needs to be done in mid-summer.	Farmers can monitor this.	There is ample evidence that these interventions work. Location of buffer strips must be considered as this affects their impact. Soil type also affects the outcome. Payment may be complicated because of the time taken to reach maximum effectiveness (5 years). Catchment scale impacts should also be considered.
<i>Breaking flow paths</i>	A visual assessment with photos (ad hoc) could be used to look for evidence of channelised flow.	Farmers can monitor this.	
<i>Improving soil structure</i>	This could be determined by measuring infiltration (with infiltrometers), water storage (by sampling soil moisture / field capacity) or reductions in fine grained sediment (visual assessment). These measurements are taken as little as once per year and/or after rainfall.	Farmers could do some of the simple monitoring, but specialists would be needed for more complex methods and analysis.	
<i>Filtering water</i>	Reductions in fine grained sediment can be measured with sampling and some laboratory analysis. This would need to be monitored monthly for adequate understanding of changes over time.	A specialist would be required given the laboratory element of this monitoring.	

Find out more about this intervention:

- Chapter 4.2 - [Working with Natural Processes – Evidence Directory](#)
- Page 9 - [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers.](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Cross drains in farm tracks

Cross drains move water across farm tracks to reduce erosion and the development of pathways for water and sediment.

Outcomes

- Improve soil infiltration / water storage
- Reduce overland flow
- Interception of water before it reaches the river
- Increase soil stability and resistance to erosion
- **Additional benefits:** Improved water quality

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a PfO Scheme
<i>Breaking flow paths</i>	A visual assessment can be undertaken (using a camera for photos) to determine the amount of channelised flow and deposition. This is on an ad hoc basis.	Farmers could monitor this.	There is some evidence that these interventions work. However, the effectiveness of them is site specific. Cumulative impacts downstream are also difficult to understand. For these reasons, payment may be difficult to calculate, but considering the whole farm impact may be a solution to this.
<i>Diverting water for infiltration</i>	A visual assessment (using a camera for photos) can be undertaken to determine flows along paths / roads etc. This is on an ad hoc basis.	Farmers could monitor this.	

Find out more about this intervention:

- Chapter 4.3 - [Working with Natural Processes – Evidence Directory](#)
- Page 13 - [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers.](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Increasing soil permeability / water holding capacity

Soil permeability and water holding capacity can be increased by aerating soils, adding organic matter, minimising tillage, and avoiding use of heavy machinery which compacts soil. These outcomes can also be achieved through [livestock management](#).

Outcomes

- Increase water storage on floodplains
- Improve soil infiltration / water storage
- Reduce overland flow
- Reduce downstream flow of water
- Improve soil conditions
- **Additional benefits:** improved water quality and greenhouse gas reduction

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a PfO Scheme
<i>Increasing infiltration</i>	Infiltration can be measured using an open pipe or a tension or double ring infiltrometer. If monitoring is not automated, it is required at least once per year, 3 days after rainfall.	Farmers can monitor this, but a specialist would be required for using more complex equipment.	There is ample evidence for many of these interventions working to a threshold. Visual assessments may complicate calculating payment bands. There are uncertainties around the effectiveness in low frequency, high magnitude flood events, as well as the effects that soil type may have. Other considerations are the variability between farms, as well as the difficulties in disentangling the efforts of each farm in affecting downstream flows.
<i>Reducing overland flow</i>	A visual assessment could be undertaken after flooding, aided by photos. Monitoring is ad-hoc.	Farmers could monitor this.	
<i>Storing water</i>	Soil field capacity (water held in soil after drainage by gravity) could be measured. This can be estimated in the field, using a probe to measure soil moisture (in winter, 3 days after a rainfall event). Samples could also be taken for gravimetric measurements, which then involves laboratory analysis.	Farmers could monitor this if trained, but specialists may be required for laboratory analysis.	
<i>Filtering water</i>	Reductions in diffuse pollution and fine grained sediment can be measured using visual assessment (and taking photos) or water quality sampling using gauge sensors. Monitoring is mostly ad hoc.	Farmers could monitor this if trained, but specialists may be required for some analysis.	
<i>Impacting downstream flow</i>	An in-stream flow gauging station would be used to determine impacts downstream.	Environment Agency.	

Find out more about this intervention:

- Page 8 - [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers](#).
[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Leaky woody dams

These are constructed in streams and ditches. They may use tree trunks and branches or may be more engineered structures. They are set either above the water level to allow baseflow to flow freely, or in contact with the bed where all flow will come into contact with it.

Outcomes

- Slow the flow of water in the watercourse
- Increase water storage on floodplains and in the channel
- Reduce downstream flow of water
- **Additional benefits:** social benefits, improved water quality, greenhouse gas reduction, and habitat provision

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a PfO Scheme
<i>Slowing flow</i>	Depth measured using time lapse photography (camera, gauge board and computer). This needs to be checked after flood events.	Anyone trained who can allocate time. Validation by a specialist is required.	There is some evidence that this intervention works, but it may be better in combination with others to make enough difference to warrant a payment scheme. The removal of sediment is important in the proper functioning of the dam and can reduce downstream sedimentation. Leaky woody dams that create a large volume of temporary water storage are more likely to be suitable for these schemes.
<i>Storing water</i>	The capacity above the dam can be measured with a tape measure or using photos, to determine storage. This would be on an ad hoc basis if structural conditions change.	Anyone trained who can allocate time. Validation by a specialist is required.	
<i>Trapping sediment</i>	The volume of sediment stored, and the rate of storage/ deposition can be measured using photographs and a bucket to collect sediment. This would be done after flood events or when the amount of sediment reaches a threshold.	Farmers can monitor this.	

Find out more about this intervention:

- Page 17 - [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers.](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Livestock management / reducing stock density

This may involve leaving more areas ungrazed to allow the land to recover and enhance water infiltration or reducing the stocking density of an area of land.

Outcomes

- Improve soil condition
- Increase soil stability and resistance to erosion
- Improve soil infiltration / water storage
- **Additional benefits:** improved water quality, greenhouse gas reduction, and habitat provision

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a PfO Scheme
<i>Increasing roughness</i>	A visual assessment could be undertaken (including taking photos) to show areas of erosion and whether these are reducing. This monitoring is on an ad hoc basis.	Farmers could monitor this.	There is some evidence that these interventions work. However, outcomes are site specific, and this may complicate the use of a payment scheme.
<i>Improving root structure</i>	Monitoring could follow a soil metrics method, specifically looking at the distribution of roots in the soil (Richardson <i>et al.</i> , 2020c). This monitoring is on an ad hoc basis.	Farmers could monitor this.	
<i>Improving soil (organic matter)</i>	A visual assessment considering earthworm counts and soil smell and texture may be used. Alternatively, laboratory analysis (i.e. loss on ignition method) could be used. This monitoring is on an ad hoc basis.	Farmers could monitor this. A specialist would be needed for any laboratory analyses though.	

Find out more about this intervention:

- Chapter 4.2 - [Working with Natural Processes – Evidence Directory](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Mob grazing

This involves grazing by a high density of stock, but over a short period. The grass then recovers over a long period, meaning the grazing is never intense on any area for too long.

Outcomes

- Improve soil condition
- Increase soil stability and resistance to erosion
- Improve soil infiltration / water storage
- **Additional benefits:** improved water quality, greenhouse gas reduction, and habitat provision

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a PfO Scheme
<i>Temporarily increasing roughness (relative to full-time grazing)</i>	This can be measured with a visual assessment of the grazed area, using a camera for photos. This would be on an ad hoc basis.	Farmers could monitor this.	There is some evidence that these interventions work to a threshold. However, complications arise from the differences between sites (soil type, stocking density etc.) This may make it difficult to devise a banded payment scheme.
<i>Improving soil structure</i>	This could be determined by measuring infiltration (with infiltrometers) or water storage (by sampling soil moisture / field capacity or using a soil metrics method. These measurements are taken as little as once per year and/or after rainfall events.	Farmers could do some of the simple monitoring, but specialists would be needed for more complex methods and analysis.	

N.B. There may be a temporarily increased flood risk immediately after the grazing period has ended.

Find out more about this intervention:

- [What is mob grazing?](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Planting and managing hedgerows

Usually used as field boundaries, hedgerows are already a key part of many landscapes. These young plants can be protected from livestock and pests using fencing if necessary.

Outcomes

- Reduce overland flow
- Interception of water before it reaches the river
- Increase soil stability and resistance to erosion
- **Additional benefits:** improved water quality, greenhouse gas reduction, and habitat provision

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a PfO Scheme
<i>Increasing roughness</i>	Vegetation height and width of understory or hedge margins can be measured using a tape measure or ruler. This needs to be done in mid-summer*.	Farmers can monitor this.	There is ample evidence that these interventions work. Location of hedgerows must be considered as this affects their impact. Payment could be based on area of understory vegetation and the effectiveness of the location. However, soil type also affects the outcome. Catchment scale impacts should be considered too.
<i>Breaking flow paths</i>	A visual assessment with photos (ad hoc) could be used to look for evidence of channelised flow.	Farmers can monitor this.	
<i>Improving soil structure</i>	This could be determined by measuring infiltration (with infiltrometers), water storage (by sampling soil moisture / field capacity or using a soil metrics method), or reductions in fine grained sediment (visual assessment). These measurements are taken as little as once per year and/or after rainfall events.	Farmers could do some of the simple monitoring, but specialists would be needed for more complex methods and analysis.	

*The efficacy of this intervention is dependent on seasonality and species, so is variable.

Find out more about this intervention:

- Chapter 4.2 - [Working with Natural Processes – Evidence Directory](#)
- Page 10 - [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers.](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Planting and managing trees

Trees may be planted in the upland areas, on the floodplain or on the riverbanks.

Outcomes

- Improve soil condition
- Interception of water before it reaches the river
- Increase soil stability and resistance to erosion
- Improve soil infiltration / water storage
- [Additional benefits](#): social benefits, improved water quality, greenhouse gas reduction, and habitat provision.

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a PfO Scheme
<i>Increasing roughness</i>	The vegetation could be monitored with photos. This would be on an ad hoc basis.	Farmers could monitor this.	There is some evidence about the effectiveness of these interventions. Different trees and soil types may have different effects, and location is key. Gauging would be needed to determine downstream impact, but it may be hard to understand cumulative impacts. This would complicate payment.
<i>Improving soil structure</i>	This could be determined by measuring infiltration (with infiltrometers) or water storage (by sampling soil moisture/field capacity or using a soil metrics method). These measurements are taken as little as once per year and / or after rainfall events.	Farmers could do some of the simple monitoring, but specialists would be needed for more complex methods and analysis.	
<i>Increasing evapotranspiration and interception</i>	Existing literature could be used to better understand roughness values and interception rates.	Specialists would be required to monitor these outcomes.	

Find out more about this intervention:

- Chapter 2.2.1 - [Natural Flood Management Handbook](#)
- Page 11 - [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers.](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Restoring meanders

Restoring the natural shape of a watercourse increases natural in channel storage of water. It can be done in most places where watercourses have previously been straightened.

Outcomes

- Slow the flow of water in the watercourse
- Reduce downstream flow of water
- **Additional benefits:** improved water quality, greenhouse gas reduction, and habitat provision

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a Pfo Scheme
<i>Slowing flow</i>	The watercourse capacity (volume) could be measured using topographic surveys and modelling studies. This would be monitored on an ad hoc basis.	Specialists would be required to monitor this outcome.	There is some evidence that this intervention works, but the effectiveness is site specific. It is perhaps unsuitable for a payment scheme due to the complications of the river crossing land ownership boundaries.

Find out more about this intervention:

- Chapter 2.2 - [Working with Natural Processes – Evidence Directory](#)
- Page 21 - [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers.](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Sediment traps

These are usually excavated in a runoff pathway. Runoff is held in the traps and sediment settles out where it can be separated from the water. This controls the release of sediment to the watercourse.

Outcomes

- Slow the flow of water in the watercourse
- **Additional benefits:** improved water quality

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a PfO Scheme
<i>Filtering water</i>	The accumulation rate and volume of sediment could be measured on an ad hoc basis to determine the functioning of the sediment trap.	Farmers can monitor this.	There is some evidence that this intervention works. However, its effectiveness depends on its intention (water quality changes, removal of nutrients etc.) as well as the location. In terms of payment schemes, this intervention may work best alongside other interventions to provide multiple benefits. This intervention may be more relevant to water quality than to flood management.

Find out more about this intervention:

- Chapter 4.4 - [Working with Natural Processes – Evidence Directory](#)
- Page 16 - [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers.](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Storage ponds

These are constructed beside watercourses, or near overland flow pathways to store water which is diverted during high flows.

Outcomes

- Slow the flow of water in the watercourse
- Increase water storage on floodplains
- Reduce downstream flow of water
- **Additional benefits:** social benefits, improved water quality, greenhouse gas reduction, and habitat provision

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a Pfo Scheme
<i>Slowing flow</i>	Storage duration measured using time lapse photography (camera, gauge board and computer). This needs to be checked after flood events.	Anyone trained who can allocate time. Validation by a specialist is required.	There is ample evidence that this intervention works. It may be possible to devise a payment scheme based on water storage volume and duration. More consideration is needed for flow rate though, and it is also difficult to understand the cumulative impacts downstream.
<i>Storing water</i>	Volume and duration of water stored can be measured by taking photos (camera and stage board needed). Photos and data should be checked after flood events.	A specialist would be required to evaluate, but farmers can monitor ongoing performance.	
<i>Trapping sediment</i>	The volume of sediment stored, and the rate of storage/ deposition can be measured using photographs and a bucket to collect and remove sediment. This would be done after flood events or when the amount of sediment reaches a threshold.	Farmers can monitor this.	

Find out more about this intervention:

- Chapter 2.4.4 - [Natural Flood Management Handbook](#)
- Page 18 - [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers.](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

Winter cover crops

Planting winter cover crops can be used in rotation with existing arable farming practices. This means the land is not left bare in the winter months, when increased erosion may occur.

Outcomes

- Improve soil condition
- Increase soil stability and resistance to erosion
- [Additional benefits](#): improved water quality, greenhouse gas reduction, and habitat provision

Monitoring Information

Outcome to monitor	Measurements, Equipment & Monitoring Frequency	Who could monitor?	Feasibility of use in a PFO Scheme
<i>Reducing diffuse pollution</i>	A visual assessment (alongside taking photos) could be undertaken on an ad hoc basis to determine the reduction of sediment deposition over winter.	Farmers could monitor this.	There is ample evidence that these interventions work to a threshold. However, their effectiveness is very much site specific. Cumulative downstream impacts may also be hard to distinguish.
<i>Increasing roughness</i>	Vegetation height can be measured with a ruler. Measurements would be on an ad hoc basis.	Farmers could monitor this.	
<i>Improving soil structure</i>	This could be determined by measuring infiltration (with infiltrometers) or water storage (by sampling soil moisture/field capacity or using a soil metrics method). These measurements are taken as little as once per year and/or after rainfall events.	Farmers could do some of the simple monitoring, but specialists would be needed for more complex methods and analysis.	
<i>Reducing overland flow</i>	A visual assessment could be undertaken after flooding, aided by photos. Monitoring is ad-hoc.	Farmers could monitor this.	

Find out more about this intervention:

- Chapter 4.2 - [Working with Natural Processes – Evidence Directory](#)
- Page 12 - [Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers.](#)

[Click here](#) to return to the start of the tool.

References

- Burgess-Gamble, L, Ngai, R., Wilkinson, M., Nisbet, T., Pontee, N., Harvey, R., Kipling, K., Addy, S., Rose, S., Maslen, S., Jay, H., Nicholson, A., Page, T., Jonczyk, J., and Quinn, P. 2018. Working with Natural Processes – Evidence Directory. Environment Agency. Available [here](#). Dasgupta, P. 2021. *The Economics of Biodiversity: The Dasgupta Review*. London: HM Treasury.
- Forbes, H., Ball, K., and McLay, F., 2015. Natural Flood Management Handbook. Scottish Environment Protection Agency. Available [here](#).
- Richardson, J.C., Armstrong, J., Sullivan, E., Keep, H., Clarke, S., Brown C., Klaar, M. 2020a. Integrating Natural Flood Management into Payment for Outcomes Schemes in the Yorkshire Dales. Available [here](#). Richardson, J., Armstrong, J., Grayson, R., Klaar, M., and Brown, C. 2020b. Farmer led monitoring: Natural Flood management toolkit. Version 1. Yorkshire Integrated Catchment Solutions Programme. Available [here](#).
- Richardson, J., Armstrong, J., Grayson, R., Klaar, M. and Brown, C. 2020c. Monitoring methodologies to evidence the functioning of interventions in payment by results trials. Available [here](#).
- Soil Association Scotland. 2021. *What is Mob grazing?*. [Online]. [Accessed 12 February 2021]. Available [here](#).
- Wingfield, T., Macdonald, N., Peters, K., Spees, J. and Potter, K. 2019. Natural flood management: Beyond the evidence debate. *Area*. **51**(4), pp.743-751.
- Yorkshire Dales National Park Authority. 2017. Natural Flood Management – a practical guide for farmers. Available [here](#).

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Appendix A – Summary of existing NFM Monitoring Guides (April 2021)

Guide	Content
Yorkshire Dales National Park: Natural Flood Management Measures – a practical guide for farmers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduces NFM. • Groups interventions into different levels. • Coverage of set up and maintenance costs. • Describes the following interventions in detail: Increasing soil permeability; Buffer strips; Planting and managing hedgerows; Using trees; Winter cover crops; Cross drains in farm tracks; Bunds and detention basins; Swales; Sediment traps; In-channel barriers; Offline flood storage ponds; Blocking moorland drainage grips; Restoring meanders; Reconnecting river with its floodplain. • Summary of consents and advice.
Environment Agency: Working with Natural Processes – Evidence Directory.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduces NFM / Working with Natural Processes. • Includes scientific confidence levels and information about multiple benefits of interventions. • Extensive coverage of a variety of NFM interventions, categorised as follows: River and floodplain management; Woodland management; Run-off management; Coasts and estuary management. • Coverage of research gaps and monitoring.
Scottish Environmental Protection Agency: Natural Flood Management Handbook.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduces NFM. • Coverage of river / catchment based interventions as well as coastal interventions. • Coverage of multiple benefits of NFM. • Details of NFM assessment, including modelling / mapping approaches. • Details about practicalities of implementing interventions and how to manage NFM projects. • Coverage of monitoring and funding.
Dales to Vale Rivers Network: Lowland Natural Flood Management Measures – a practical guide for farmers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on Yorkshire Dales National Park: Natural Flood Management Measures – a practical guide for farmers (above). • Contents are the same as this guide, but with slightly amended interventions covered: Increasing soil health (reducing compaction and managing in arable rotation); Buffer strips, Planting and managing hedgerows; Ditch management; Using trees; Winter cover crops; Cross drains in farm tracks; Bunds and detention basins; Swales; Sediment traps; In-channel barriers; Offline flood storage ponds; Ditch / Dyke restoration and management; Wetland Creation; Reconnecting the river with its floodplain; Restoring meanders.

[Yorkshire Dales Rivers Trust: Advice and Guidance for different NFM techniques.](#)

- Advice and guidance for the following interventions: Leaky dams; Earth Bunds; Tree planting; Buffer strips; Hedge planting.
- Description of intervention.
- Advice on intervention design and key points to consider.
- Location factors and advice on consents.
- Case study of intervention use.
- Some details about costs.
- An outline of maintenance.